

Synthesis of some transition metal complexes with 4-(phenyl/*p*-bromophenyl)thiazolyldrazone of *o*-anisaldehyde

D. C. Dash*, A. K. Panda, P. Jena, S. B. Patjoshi and A. Mohapatra

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla-768 019, India

Manuscript received 12 September 2000, accepted 20 April 2001

Complexes of type ML_2X_2 , where L = 2-(*o*-anisylideneiminoamino)-4-phenylthiazole (APT) or 2-(*o*-anisylideneiminoamino)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiazole (ABPT); M = Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} have been synthesised. The results are consistent with bidentate chelation of the ligand with azomethine nitrogen and ring sulfur atoms as bonding sites, the complexes are in an approximately octahedral environment. The symmetry being C_2 for the Co^{II} complexes and D_{4h} for other complexes. Crystal field parameters for the Co^{II} and tetragonal parameters for the Ni^{II} complexes have been calculated.

As a part of our research on the studies of metal complexes with bioactive ligands containing NOS donor¹, we report here synthetic and structural studies on the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with some hydrazone derivatives containing thiazole moiety, such as 2-(*o*-anisaldehydeiminoamino)-4-phenyl-thiazole (APT) and 2-(*o*-anisaldehydeiminoamino)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiazole (ABPT).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data exhibit 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry for all the metal complexes and the low molar conductance (in DMSO) values indicate them to be non-electrolytes (Table 1).

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % : Found (Calcd)	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
$Co(APT)_2Cl_2$	Purple	7.81 (7.86)	10.14
$Co(APT)_2Br_2$	Green	7.02 (7.04)	8.26
$Co(APT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Grey	7.32 (7.36)	7.24
$Co(ABPT)_2Cl_2$	Pink	6.48 (6.51)	23.08
$Co(ABPT)_2Br_2$	Pink	5.88 (5.92)	19.02
$Co(ABPT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Violet	6.12 (6.15)	23.66
$Ni(APT)_2Cl_2$	Green	7.82 (7.85)	9.60
$Ni(APT)_2Br_2$	Ivory	7.02 (7.02)	9.80
$Ni(APT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Green	7.31 (7.33)	10.20
$Ni(ABPT)_2Cl_2$	Blue	6.48 (6.52)	22.10
$Ni(ABPT)_2Br_2$	Blue	5.88 (5.91)	26.20
$Ni(ABPT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Green	7.11 (7.08)	20.82
$Cu(APT)_2Cl_2$	Grey	8.42 (8.44)	12.60
$Cu(APT)_2Br_2$	Yellow	7.52 (7.55)	11.20
$Cu(APT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Brown	7.86 (7.88)	11.60
$Cu(ABPT)_2Cl_2$	Green	6.94 (6.97)	21.91
$Cu(ABPT)_2Br_2$	Green	6.48 (6.51)	22.64
$Cu(ABPT)_2(NO_3)_2$	Blue	6.54 (6.59)	21.84

All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

IR spectra :

IR spectra were recorded in KBr. The formation of ligands APT and ABPT through condensation of *o*-anisaldehyde with 2-hydrazino-4-phenyl/*p*-bromophenylthiazole was confirmed by the disappearance of ν_{NH_2} bands and appearance of a new band at 1600 cm^{-1} , originating due to newly introduced azomethine (C=N) group. The presence of OCH_3 group in APT/ABPT is also indicated² by the appearance of bands at 2840 cm^{-1} .

It is interesting to note here that introduction of an electron-releasing group like OCH_3 in APT/ABPT near the condensation site only enhances the conjugation as suggested by the appearance of more intense $\nu_{C=N}$ band without participating in complexation probably due to steric reason.

Further, IR spectra of the ligands show multiple bands at $3200\text{--}3060 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to N-H and C-H stretching vibrations of imino NH, phenyl and thiazolyl groups. The position of this band system remains unaltered in the present complexes indicating non-involvement of imino nitrogen atom in complexation. The ligand bands ~ 1540 , ~ 1310 and 850 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ (cyclic), ν_{C-N} and C-S-C mode of vibration thiazole moiety. The position of the later band shifted to lower frequency region by $10\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes, whereas the former two bands remained practically unaltered indicating the coordination of ring sulfur atom to the metal ion. Besides, the bands at 1600 and 1010 cm^{-1} (azomethine C=N and N-N) shifted their position on complexation. The $\nu_{C=N}$ band showed red-shift whereas ν_{N-N} band showed blue-shift thereby implying the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ion. Therefore, the IR data reveals that the ligands APT and ABPT act as a neutral bidentate ligand; the bonding sites being azomethine nitrogen and ring sulfur atom leading to the bis-complex of the type $ML_2(X_3)_2$. IR

spectral evidence for the bonding of the anionic part is as follows. In the nitrate complexes four additional band at 1380, 1040, 810 and 770 cm^{-1} were observed. These spectral features provide unequivocal evidence for coordination of nitrate group in an unidentate manner under C_{2v} symmetry³. The coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom and nitrate anion through oxygen atom is further confirmed by the presence of bands at 520 (M-N) and 460 cm^{-1} (M-O).

Although evidence of M-S, M-Cl, M-Br bonds could not be brought out in the present investigation, the insolubility of the complexes in water and their non-electrolytic nature provide sufficient evidence for covalency of the counter anion.

Thermal analysis :

Thermal data of the complexes formed by APT and ABPT with chlorides as counter ion were recorded. An examination of thermogram of APT complexes reveal that the complexes remained almost stable upto 230–260° indicating absence of water molecules. Beyond this range the complexes decomposed rapidly leaving a stable residue (metal oxide) in the case of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The Cu^{II} complex did not form any stable residue and the decomposition continued beyond 620°. Thermogram of ABPT complexes revealed their stability upto 220–290° indicating the absence of water molecules. Beyond this range they showed rapid decomposition, denoting loss of ligand moiety. However, they do not adhere to constant weight due to decomposition even upto ~620°.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

Co^{II} complexes : The room temperature μ_{eff} values lie in the range 4.42–4.72 B.M. for the Co^{II} complexes which are below the lower limit of the high-spin pseudo-octahedral Co^{II} complexes. These values imply that they had probably an orbital singlet ground state with distorted octahedral environment as evident by the electronic spectral data. The electronic spectra (nujol) of these complexes showed a broad band at 9000–10000 and doubly split band at 19000–21000 which may be assigned to ν_1 and ν_3 transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, in O_h symmetry.

The split components of ν_3 band suggest the structure having lower symmetry than O_h (approx. C_2)⁴. The calculated value of ν_2 band suggests the band to be very close to ν_3 band and hence remained unobserved in the present cases. In the ν_1 band region although no visible splitting was observed, and as expected the appearance of the band in the region as broad envelop suggests superimposition of different components of C_2 symmetry into single one.

Ni^{II} complexes : The room temperature μ_{eff} values of the Ni^{II} complexes lie in the range 2.83–3.4 B.M. expected for tetragonal six-coordinated spin-free Ni^{II} species. The electronic spectral (nujol) of APT complexes showed a

number of bands at ~8600, ~10400, ~14000, 15000 and 26000 cm^{-1} . The first two bands are assigned to transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, the split components of ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$, the third and fourth bands are assigned to transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, the split components of ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ term, whereas the last may be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition, the ground term A_{2g} under O_h symmetry being transformed to ${}^3B_{2g}$ term under D_{4h} symmetry⁵. The values of tetragonal parameters D_t , D_s in-plane and out-of-plane strength D_q^E and D_q^A , Δ_{eg}^E and Δ_{eg}^A have been calculated on the basis of crystal field approximation⁵. The results are shown in the Table 2.

Table 2. Tetragonal parameter (cm^{-1}) of $\text{Ni}(\text{APT})_2\text{X}_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{ABPT})_2\text{X}_2$ complexes

Compd.	D_t	D_q^E	D_q^A	D_s	Δ_{eg}^E	Δ_{eg}^A
$\text{Ni}(\text{APT})_2\text{Cl}_2$	205.7	1040	679.9	226.18	2624	-272
$\text{Ni}(\text{ABPT})_2\text{Cl}_2$	251	1060	620	303	2467	-346
$\text{Ni}(\text{APT})_2\text{Br}_2$	204.5	1028	669.9	225.9	2477	-356
$\text{Ni}(\text{ABPT})_2\text{Br}_2$	256	1054	606	353	2992	-221
$\text{Ni}(\text{APT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	203.4	1032	675.9	312.3	2673	-209
$\text{Ni}(\text{ABPT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	254	1043	597	336	2614	-262

Cu^{II} complexes : The μ_{eff} values at room temperature lie in the range 1.82–1.90 B.M. expected for distorted octahedral Cu^{II} complexes. However, the electronic spectra of the complexes are not similar. The electronic of $\text{Cu}(\text{APT})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ABPT})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ABPT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, exhibited two bands at 13750–14290 and 15000–16670 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition, respectively. However the bromo complexes showed one broad envelope at 13500–14300 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ whereas $\text{Cu}(\text{APT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex showed three bands at 11110, 13510 and 16670 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, under D_{4v} symmetry. Based on the foregoing observations and considering the *trans* arrangement of the ligands in the complex molecules to be more stable than the *cis* arrangement because of the steric strain, the following tentative structure may be proposed for the complexes :

M

= Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II}

X = Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^-

Experimental

The chemicals used were reagent grade. The starting materials 2-hydrazino-4-(phenylthiazole) and 2-hydrazino-4-(*p*-bromophenylthiazole) were prepared by refluxing

ethanolic solution of phenacyl bromide and *p*-bromophenacyl bromide, respectively, with thiosemicarbazide. The hydrazones were obtained as coloured solids by refluxing the above hydrazones with *o*-anisaldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol in presence of a few drops of piperidine. The complexes were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of the ligand, APT or ABPT (0.004 mol) with the corresponding hydrated metal(II) salt (0.002 mole dissolved in the same solvent) on a water-bath with stirring for 2–3 h (2 h for the copper complexes and ~3 h for other complexes), then filtered and allowed to cool. The resulting crystals were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride.

Acknowledgement

Grateful thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the

award of a Teacher Fellowship to one of the authors (P.J.) and financial support under major research project.

References

1. D. C. Dash, R. K. Behera, M. Sen and F. M. Meher, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 663; D. C. Dash, A. K. Panda, H. Mohanty and P. Ranjitha-Kumari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 791; D. C. Dash, F. M. Meher, P. C. Mohanty and J. Nanda, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 698; D. C. Dash, F. M. Meher and P. C. Mohanty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **63**, 939.
2. R. V. Singh and J. Tandon, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **26**, 602.
3. R. L. Carlin, "Transition Metal Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1965.
4. A. B. P. Lever and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 859.
5. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.